

INFLUENCE OF OWNERSHIP CONCENTRATION ON INTEGRATED REPORTING OF NON-FINANCIAL SERVICES FIRMS IN NIGERIA: MODERATING INFLUENCE OF FIRM VALUE

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to examine the moderating effect of firm value on the relationship between ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. The study adopted correlational research design and the population of the study comprises of 105 non-financial services firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange as at 31 December 2021. From this population, a sample of 58 non-financial services firms were selected as the sample of the study. The duration of the study is 10 years, 2012 to 2021 and secondary data extracted from the sampled firms were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The study found a strong and positive association between ownership concentration and integrated reporting. However, when firm value was introduced as a moderating variable, the relationship between ownership concentration and integrated reporting became strongly inverted. Hence, this study concludes that ownership concentration in highly valued firms may reduce integrated reporting. This study therefore recommends that the regulatory bodies in Nigeria should create greater awareness on integrated reporting to increase the participation of ownership concentration in its adoption.

KEYWORDS: ownership concentration, integrated reporting, firm value, firm size.

1. Introduction

Integrated reporting (IR) is the most recent development in sustainability reporting. According to Rupley et al. (2017), integrated reporting (IR) links past performance of the firm with its future outlook while Adams (2017) opined that IR is a paradigm shift curtailing what firms think about business operations and value creation. IR is a new management-reporting tool, better explains the association between the firm and the stakeholders with greater focus on the investors through integrated thinking (Raimo et al., 2020). Thus, through integrated thinking, financial report and non-financial report of firms are integrated into a single report that portrays the holistic operations of the firm and their inter connections. IR is a reporting tool that is capable of giving information about governance, risks, opportunities, strategy, performance, and future prospects with all its inter-connections (IIRC, 2013).

Ownership concentration (OC) is a tool for controlling the stewardship of management because more powers are vested with the majority shareholders. These powers grant them accessibility to information thereby reducing information asymmetry and the need for voluntary disclosure (Zouari & Dhifi, 2021). Yunus (2011) argued that ownership concentration (OC) has incentive to protect their investments with the tendency to disclose less information on earnings to reduce external monitoring of their business activities. However, Gomes (2000) asserted that expropriation activities might cost ownership concentration their investment and the value of the firm may decrease when minority shareholders discount their shares. Hence, in order to enhance the image of the firm, OC may support investment in corporate social responsibility (CSR) and IR, which may cause an increase in the value of the firm in the long run.

Moreover, firm value (FV) is an important consideration for investors because the survival of the company is hinged on its value (Liestyasih & Wiagustini, 2017). According to Markonah et al. (2020), firm value is the fair value of a company that explains the perception of the success of the organization depicted by stock prices. Since FV is a reflection of the perception of investors' using the share price, it is pertinent for management to consider integrated reporting disclosure (Marita et al., 2020). The value of the firm tends to affect IR because investors are more willing to invest in firms that are more transparent in their disclosure (Alade & Odugbemi, 2022). Hence, willingness to retain high value encourages managers to engage in IR (Marita et al., 2020). Thus, FV was used as the moderating variable due to the above considerations. In order to enhance the robustness of this study, firm size (FZ) was introduced as a control variable to adjust for controversies that might arise due to the size of the selected companies. According to Ahmed-Haji and Anifowose (2016), firm size is strongly connected to financial and non-financial reporting practices due to their level of visibility.

Statement of the Problem

Notably, the non-financial services sector of the Nigerian economy serves as an anchor for the provision of goods and services to the Nigerian populace thereby ensuring quality of lives and general economic growth of the nation. Despite the provision of these importance services to the Nigerian populace, companies in the non-financial services sector have witnessed several financial scandals, which had slowed down its growth and thus loosing investors' trusts. Notable among them is the Cadbury saga of 2008, the Skye bank scandal, the Diamond takeover by Access bank and most recently, the sanction of Flour Mills Plc and Stanbic IBTC by the Nigerian Exchange for not disclosing price sensitive information in their annual reports (Oyong et al., 2022). These ugly events have dwindled the ability of investors to rely on the annual reports of these corporations for decision making. Nonetheless, the IR concept emerged to rectify the shortfalls of the present corporate reporting outlines. Thus, based on the above, this study aimed to examine the moderating

effect of firm value on ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Owing to the growing relevance of IR, several scholars in extant literature examined integrated reporting in both developed and emerging economies (Burc et al., 2018; Chariri&Januarti, 2017; Dilling&Caykolu, 2019; Mähönen, 2020; Othman et al., 2022; Oyong et al., 2022) however, very few of these scholars investigated the relationship between integrated reporting and ownership concentration. More so, majority of these few studies (Injeni et al., 2019; Isnurhadi et al., 2020; Kong et al., 2020; Pandey and Sahu, 2019; Raimo et al., 2020) considered the direct relationship between ownership concentration and integrated reporting and their findings were inconsistent. Thus creating a gap in literature in the field of ownership structure and integrated reporting around the world economies and specifically in Nigeria. This research hoped to close this gap by empirically examining the effect of ownership concentration on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria using a moderating variable. A moderating variable is a variable the strengthen the relationship between dependent variable and the independent variable. In this study, firm value was used to moderate the association between ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Further, to enhance the robustness of this study, firm size (FZ) was introduced as a control variable to adjust for controversies that might arise due to the size of the selected companies. According to Ahmed-Haji and Anifowose (2016), firm size is strongly connected to financial and non-financial reporting practices due to their level of visibility.

Objective and Purpose of the Study

The major objective of this study is to examine the effect OC on IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria with FV as the moderating variable and the specific objectives are to:

- i. Investigate the effect of OC on IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria
- ii. Evaluate the effect of FV on OC of non-financial services firms in Nigeria
- iii. Examine the moderating effect of FV and OC on IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

To achieve the above objectives, the following hypotheses are formulated:

Ho₁: Ownership concentration has no significant effect on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Firm value has no significant effect on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Moderating effect of firm value on ownership concentration has no significant effect on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study would be relevant to the regulatory bodies and policy makers of non-financial services firms in Nigeria by enabling them make decisions that would increase the enlightenment of OC relating to the benefits of IR in order to ensure the disclosure of IR among non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Further, the findings of this study will aid the management of non-financial services firms' affirm the needs of block owners in order to protect the minority shareholders. Furthermore, this study will be an addition to the body of knowledge on ownership concentration and integrated reporting in Nigeria and serve as a reference for further studies.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Ownership Concentration and Integrated Reporting

According to Raimo et al (2020), IR demonstrate the ability of a company to create value within the short, medium, and long terms. IR is the representation of the existing relationship amid the company and the stakeholders particularly the investors. Further, Eccles and Armbruster(2010) viewed IR as the practice of incorporating environmental, social, and governance reports into single annual reports of firms. IR is a single report that presents both financial and non-financial information on one hand and how value could be created (Eccles & Krzus, 2010). Similarly, Sierra-Garcia (2015) argued that IR does not only reflect financial and non-financial information but also reveals a company's operational strategy. Equally, Hoque (2017) affirmed that IR is a tool for building a sustainable society.

Ownership concentration means the concentration of large numbers of shares in the hands of few individuals, which gives these individuals strong power on the organization over and above other shareholders. With this power, they are able to acquire information directly from the managers. Therefore, the dominating shareholders do not need published reports to obtain the information they want (Jensen & Berg, 2012; Hahn & Kühnen, 2013). As such, the company may not consider it necessary to voluntarily disclose financial and non-financial information. In contrast to OC, Meuleman (2018) opined that dispersed ownership favor IR because IR reduce agency cost by bridging the gap between the managers of the firm and the owners. In a related development, Jensen and Berg (2012) studied determinants of traditional sustainability reporting and integrated reporting using the institutionalist approach. Using a sample of 309 organizations drawn from a population of companies who prepare sustainability report around the world, the study found an inverse relationship amid ownership concentration and integrated reporting.

Firm Value and Integrated Reporting

According to Priya and Mohanasundari (2016) and Veda and Panji (2021), the main aim of organizations is to optimize shareholders' wealth, which is usually reflected in the share price. Firm value is the firm's efforts to increase the shareholders' fund and the firm's capacity to utilize the funds invested in generating earnings (Sualekhkhattak & Hussain, 2017). It is an economic measure that reflects the market value of a firm, which represents the perceptions of investors in relation to the worth of the firm. FV consists of both financial and non-financial indicators that proffer information on the extent to which firms attain objectives and results. The firm value comprises owners' equity and creditors for loans, advances, and trade.

Nurkumalasari et al. (2019) investigated integrated reporting and firm value of Asian firms by extracting secondary data from the annual reports of a sample of non-financial services companies in the Asian region covering a period of 3 years, 2015 to 2017. Using moderation regression analysis, the results showed that integrated reporting does not affect the firm value of companies in Asia. In addition, Adegbeie et al. (2019) studied the evaluation of integrated reporting and the value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Using a population of 53 listed manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian exchange out of which 38 firms were selected as the sample size of the study. Secondary data covering a period of 5 years, from 2012 to 2016. Employing multiple regression analysis for the analysis of data, the study found a significant association between integrated reporting and the firm value of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ownership Concentration, Firm Value, and Integrated Reporting

Firm value is influenced by the insights of owners on the ability of managers to anticipate and respond to future developments in the firm's economic environment (Emeka-Nwokeji, 2019). Moreover, Meuleman (2018) affirmed that firm value comprises of three layers namely; financial value, shared value and societal values. These values could be better enhanced through value creation in IR. To corroborate this statement, Marita et al. (2020) asserted that among the benefits of IR is to increase the value of the firm through value creation. Most often, investment decisions made by investors do not constitute financial information alone rather; it incorporates both financial and non-financial indices, which constitutes the focus of IR.

Kong et al. (2020) studied corporate governance mechanisms, ownership structure, and firm value of quoted Chinese firms using secondary data extracted from the annual reports of 871 sampled firms. The sample, which covered a period of 7 years, 2010 to 2016 was drawn from a population of 3356 companies listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges. The results reveal a positive association between ownership concentration and firm value. Moreover, Sun et al. (2022) empirically tested the effect of multiple capital disclosure on capital market using integrated reporting perspective of Chinese firms, by selecting a sample 247 of A-share firms listed on the Chinese Stock Exchange for a period of 5 years, 2012 to 2016, secondary data were extracted from the annual reports of the sampled companies and multiple linear regression was used to analyze the data. The results revealed that integrated reporting disclosure of multiple capitals led to a positive increase in the firm value of Chinese organizations.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

As an important corporate governance mechanism, ownership structure has remained in literature as one of the means of mitigating agency costs. According to agency theory, the divergence of interest between management and owners of businesses may retard the growth of the business and cause information asymmetry because management may make decisions that favor their interest in order to gain recognition and earn more bonuses, thereby ignoring the need of the owners for capital appreciation as well as revenue. In line with the agency theory, ownership concentration abets integrated reporting by focusing on strategic decisions that maximize firm value (Dhifi & Zouari, 2022). Notably, a higher level of disclosure and more transparent reporting in addition to the credibility and reliability of the information presented by IR tends to reduce the gap of information asymmetry between management and the owners thereby decreasing agency cost (Angelstig & Gustavsson, 2016). Thus, agency theory has been adopted as the theoretical basis of this study. As seen in the works of Kong et al. (2020), Moloji and Iredele (2020), and Olalere (2022)

3. METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design is adopted by this study to examine the moderating effect of firm value and ownership concentration on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria with firm size as a control variable. Due to the fact that integrated reporting is still at the voluntary disclosure stage in Nigeria, content analysis technique was applied to examine the moderating effect of firm value on the relationship between ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. On this premise, the extent to which the information contained in the annual reports of the sampled firms are checked in relation to the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) framework checklist carried out by previous scholars (Donkor et al., 2021; IIRC, 2012; Zhou et al., 2017), the checklist (Appendix A III) was centered around the content elements (presented based on the guiding principles of IIRC (2012)).

Thus, to extract the data, consideration is made on the availability of 8 guiding principles, which comprised of the content element of IR (organizational overview and operating context, governance, opportunity and risks, strategy and resource allocation, business model, performance and outcomes, future outlook, and basis of preparation and presentation) in the annual reports of sampled firms. Based on these, this study extracted secondary data from the annual reports of 58 non-financial services firms sampled out of a population of 105 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange covering a period of 10 years, 2012 to 2021. The proclamation of integrated reporting in 2011 justified the duration of the study while the sample size was drawn from a population of 105 non-financial services firms quoted on the Nigerian Exchange. The sample size was selected based on the availability of appropriate data needed for the study to adequately examine the causal effects among the variables. The study employed multiple regression analysis as the technique of data analysis.

Model Specification: The model of the study is specified below:

$$IR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OC_{it} + \beta_2 FV_{it} + \beta_3 FZ_{it} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$IR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OC_{it} + \beta_2 FV_{it} + \beta_3 OCFV_{it} + \beta_4 FZ_{it} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

From the model, IR connotes integrated reporting; OC means ownership concentration; FV depicts firm value, and FZ implies firm size. Similarly, i represents company subscript, t denotes year script, β_0 connotes constant while $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ implies coefficient of intercept and μ signifies error term.

IR was proxy by IR index using the occurrence method of content analysis; when an element of IR is present in the annual reports of the sampled firms; it scored 1 and 0 when otherwise and the total summed and divided by the total elements on the checklist. More so, OC was measured as 5% or more shares owned by block shareholders in relation to the total number of shares in issue. Additionally, FV is depicted by Tobin's Q and FZ was measured as total logarithm of fixed assets.

4. Result and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics: Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the data. Descriptive statistics simply describe the data by analyzing the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation of the data on ownership concentration integrated reporting and firm value.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observations	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
IR	580	0.4803	0.1811	0.645	0.8065
OC	580	0.562	0.2224	0	1
FV	580	1.5973	1.3963	0.3423	11.7568
FZ	580	10.2972	0.7762	8.4179	12.3788

Source: STATA 13

As indicated in Table 1, the results of the descriptive statistics show that under the period of study, the mean value of IR is 0.48 with a minimum of 0.64 and a maximum of 0.80. This means that the IR disclosure of non-financial services firms in Nigeria within the period of the study stood at an average of 48% with a minimum disclosure of 64% and as high as 80% disclosure of IR. Indicating that most Nigerian non-financial services firms voluntarily disclose non-financial information in their annual reports. The minimum number of OC of non-financial services firms in Nigeria stood at 0 and a maximum of 1 during the period of review with an average of 0.56. This result implies that non-financial services firms in Nigeria is 56% owned by OC and further implies that a majority of Nigerian non-financial services firms are controlled by block owners who hold more

than half of the total shares of non-financial services companies and thus have a strong hold on the operations of such firms.

On average, FV of non-financial services firms stood at a ratio of 1.6 with a minimum of 0.34 and a maximum of 11.8 implying that during the period of the study, the firm value of non-financial services firms in Nigeria is relatively low considering the range between the maximum value and the minimum value of the companies.

Correlation Analysis: The correlation result of the data, which depicts the association between the dependent and independent variables of the study, is presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Correlation Matrix

Variables	IR	OC	FV	FZ
IR	1.0000			
OC	0.13555	1.0000		
FV	0.1366	0.1848	1.0000	
FZ	0.4655	0.2266	0.0543	1.0000

Source: STATA 13

From Table 2, it can be seen that the associations between the dependent variable and the independent variables are minimal. Additionally, the relationship between the independent variables are also insignificant thus indicating the absence of multicollinearity among the variables of the study. Notably, it can be deduced from Table 2 that there exists a minimal relationship between OC, FV, FZ, and IR of non-financial services companies in Nigeria.

Results of Diagnostics Tests: To enhance the validity of all statistical inferences from the data, diagnostics tests were conducted and presented in this section. The mean variance inflation factor of 1.01 depicted the absence of multicollinearity among the variables of the study. More so, the Chi² probability of 0.0002 obtained from the Breusch-Pagan test was significant indicating that the data has panel effect. Hence, the inability to interpret the ordinary least square regression result necessitated further tests. The Hausman Specification Test was conducted and the result indicated a Chi² probability of 0.074, which is significant. Hence, implying the interpretation of the fixed effect model (Adegbe et al., 2019).

Results: The regression result derived from the data of ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria is presented in Table 3

Table 3
Regression analysis

Variables	Co-efficient	t-statistics	p-value	Cumulative results
IR	-3.8498	-12.57	0.0000	
OC	0.1832	3.35	0.001	
FV	0.1204	2.11	0.035	
OCFV	-0.1547	-1.75	0.081	
FZ	0.2985	10.15	0.0000	
R ²				0.19
Adjusted R ²				0.18
Prob				0.0000

Source: STATA 13

As depicted in Table 3, the R² stood at 0.19, meaning that 19% of the overall variation in integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria is determined by the independent variable and

the moderating variable (ownership concentration and firm value) of the study. The χ^2 of 0.0000, which is significant at 1% indicates that the model of ownership concentration, integrated reporting, and firm value with firm size as a control variable is fit and implies that there exists a 99.9% probability that the relationship between the variables (ownership concentration, integrated reporting, firm value, and firm size) is not a mere coincidence, such that the independent variables (OC, FV, FZ) reliably predict the dependent variable (IR) of the study.

As indicated in Table 3, OC has a t-value of 3.35 with a coefficient of 0.1832 and a p-value of 0.01, which is significant at 1%. This result shows a significant association between OC and IR, thereby connoting that an increase in OC will lead to a significant increase in IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that OC does not significantly affect IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria, is hereby rejected. This result can be substantiated by the fact that block owners would normally want to look good in the eyes of the public and regulators, hence, in order to boost their image as well as the image of the firm, OC may put pressure on the management to invest in CSR and endorse IR. This finding is in line with the works of Adegbe et al. (2019), Dhifi and Zouari (2022), and Injeni et al. (2019). While it is in variance with the works of Isnurhadi et al. (2020), Jensen and Berg (2012), Rahimo et al. (2020).

Furthermore, FV has a t-value of 2.11 with a coefficient of 0.1204 and a p-value of 0.035 and it is significant at 1%. Implying that, there exists a significant relationship between FV and IR. Further indicating an increase in FV would lead to a significant increase in IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. In this vein, the null hypothesis, which states that FV does not significantly affect IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria, is thus rejected. This result is corroborated by the fact that IR offers more transparent and reliable information to the stakeholders thereby enabling them make the right decisions regarding their investments. This result is in tandem with the findings of Moloji and Iredele (2020), Sun et al. (2022), and Utomo et al. (2020). While inconsistent with the findings of Abdolkhani and Jalali (2013), Nurkumalasari et al. (2019), and Sahrul and Novita (2020).

Furthermore, the regression result of OCFV reveals a t-value of -1.75 with a coefficient of -0.1547 and a p-value of 0.081, which is significant at 1% implying that a 1% increase in the combined effect of OC and FV will lead to a significant decrease in integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that the moderating effect of FV on OC does not affect IR of non-financial services firms in Nigeria, is thus rejected. This result clearly shows that the moderating variable (firm value) is able to moderate the relationship between ownership concentration and integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria because going by the initial result of the relationship (OC & IR) without the moderating variable in appendix IV, the association between OC and IR was insignificant but with the introduction of the moderating variable, the association became influential and strong although inverted.

This result further buttresses the fact that the presence of many block holders in highly valued organizations tends to reduce the adoption of integrated reporting (Zouari & Dhifi, 2021). This is because, ownership concentration holds a strong influence on the management due to corporate governance, which gives them more access to privileged information about the company. Hence, when the firm value is increasing, ownership concentration may not be bothered about more information through IR, whose adoption may cause the incursion of additional costs.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of ownership concentration on integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria with firm value as the moderating variable. This finding indicates that the value of the firm determines the influence of ownership concentration on integrated reporting and any significant increase in ownership concentration will cause a significant decrease in integrated reporting of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. As seen from the empirical analysis, although ownership concentration can cause an increase in the

disclosure of integrated reporting by non-financial services firms in Nigeria, the higher the firm value, the lower will be the level of disclosure of integrated reporting by non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Based on the above findings, this study therefore recommends and concludes that more awareness of the intrinsic benefits of IR be created by the regulatory bodies in Nigeria to encourage block owners to acknowledge its importance and thus encourage non-financial services firms to adopt integrated reporting when the value of the firm is increasing for optimum shareholders; investment returns.

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